

Developing a website for English-speaking practice to English as a foreign language learners at the university level

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the adaptation of the analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation (ADDIE) instructional model in designing and developing a website for the speaking practice of English as a foreign language (EFL) student at the university level. The feasibility of the website was measured through the evaluation of independent experts from three aspects of rating: web design, instructional content, and language usage. Six expert lecturers and 64 EFL students were invited to assess the website. Of these lecturers, two have expertise in multimedia and informatics, while the other four include two specialists in English instructional content and two in English linguistics. The assessments exposed that the web is easy to use by students and very practical in supporting students for learning; the content of learning material in the website has manifested the syllabus of English-speaking skill on the specified level; and the language used by the website is matched with the level of students' language proficiency. Therefore, this study successfully developed a prototype of a web-based language learning product that helps students practice English speaking at the intermediate level.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The advent of digital technology has revolutionized the field of education, making learning resources more accessible and interactive. In language learning, especially English as a foreign language (EFL), there is a growing need for innovative methods to enhance students' speaking skills, an area often neglected in traditional classroom settings. Speaking fluency is crucial for effective communication in English, yet it remains a significant challenge for many learners due to limited opportunities for practice and the absence of conducive learning platforms.

Research has shown that web-based learning platforms can significantly enhance language acquisition by providing learners with a flexible and interactive environment [1]–[3]. Previous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of combining multimedia elements—such as videos, audio recordings, and interactive exercises—in language learning tools [4]. However, despite these advancements, a notable gap remains in providing dedicated platforms for speaking practice, particularly at the intermediate level. The need for a comprehensive tool that integrates various speaking practice models—such as integrated and independent speaking practices—remains unmet. Current EFL platforms predominantly focus on reading, listening, and writing skills, with minimal resources dedicated to speaking [5]. Moreover, most existing platforms do not tailor their content to the specific needs of intermediate learners, who require more advanced and contextually relevant materials [6]. Therefore, studies like [7], [8] support that incorporating multimodal learning

experiences can significantly enhance learners' engagement and retention. By leveraging the cognitive and pedagogical benefits of multimedia content, the website developed in this study aims to support speaking practice, particularly for intermediate learners, highlighting a critical need for integrated and contextually relevant speaking tools. In addition, it also provides an enriched learning environment that supports the cognitive integration of auditory and visual information, thus enhancing comprehension and retention [9].

Existing literature underscores the importance of using technology in language education. For instance, Chapelle and Voss [10] argued that computer-assisted language learning (CALL) offers unique opportunities for practice and interaction that are often missing in traditional classroom environments. Furthermore, language learning platforms like Duolingo and Rosetta Stone, although successful in providing broad-spectrum language learning, often lack the depth and specificity needed for intermediate-level learners [11]. By focusing on specific models of speaking practice and integrating a systematic development approach, the website developed in this study aims to provide a more tailored learning experience. Similarly, research on multimedia learning by Sweller [12] emphasizes the importance of reducing cognitive load by presenting information through multiple channels, a principle that underpins the design of website platform in the study in-hand. By offering both integrated and independent speaking practice models, the platform addresses different learning needs and preferences, providing a balanced approach to skill development [13], [14].

The website developed in this study is grounded in the analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation (ADDIE) model, a systematic approach widely recognized for its effectiveness in instructional design [15]. The ADDIE model ensures a thorough understanding of learner needs and systematically translates these into an educational tool that can be iteratively refined. Other studies [13], [16], [17] have also highlighted the advantages of using structured instructional design models in developing educational technologies. Specifically, Shakeel *et al.* [18] illustrated the practicality of the ADDIE model in blended learning environments within the technical and vocational education and training (TVET) sector in Bangladesh, emphasizing its adaptability and structured content delivery. Similarly, Ghani and Daud [19] successfully applied the ADDIE model to develop a specialized platform for Arabic language learning, thus further validating its utility in language education contexts. By systematically applying the ADDIE model to develop a focused and interactive learning platform, this study aims to bridge the existing gaps in speaking practice resources. To achieve this aim, the study undertook several specific objectives: i) conduct a thorough needs analysis to comprehend the students' requirements and preferences; ii) design a user-friendly and pedagogically sound web platform for English-speaking practice; iii) develop interactive and contextually relevant learning materials tailored to intermediate level of EFL students; iv) implement the platform with a target group of EFL students; and v) evaluate the platform's effectiveness and gather feedback through expert and user assessments.

2. METHOD

This study used a R&D research method. The R&D or the acronym letters for research and development is a systematic and iterative process that combines investigative research and practical development to create, test, and refine technological products aimed at enhancing educational experiences [15]. The R&D method used by this study aims to create a prototype product in education; that is a website for speaking practice of EFL. In line with the product to be generated, researchers used an approach named ADDIE model [20] in the research development. ADDIE is a popular term for a systematic approach to instructional development in education. The ADDIE stands for analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation [21]. Therefore, the research procedure underwent those five phases to attain the prototype product as shown in Figure 1.

The analysis phase is to analyze students' needs for learning English, specifically focusing on speaking skills. In this phase, researchers conducted a needs analysis through surveys, prepared a set of ten questions focusing on learning materials, content, and platform preferences. Then, they administered the survey to students during their intermediate English speaking (IES) course. Data collected were from student responses on the difficulty of learning materials, students' preferences for content format, and their experiences with Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and web-based learning. These survey data were analyzed to identify common needs and preferences, in addition to determine the necessity and feasibility of developing a web-based platform for speaking practice.

In the design phase, researchers designed a conceptual framework for the website by reviewing the course syllabus and instructional models, making layout and flow using wireframes and mock-ups, and consulting with ICT experts to optimize user experience. In the development phase, researchers developed and populated the website with appropriate content by registering the domain of the website, developing the website using web development tools and technologies (i.e., HTML, CSS, JavaScript). Also, in this phase instructional videos, audio recordings, reading materials, and speaking prompts were integrated into the website while ensuring the website has included features such as user authentication, audio recording, and storage.

Then, the implementation phase is to deploy the website and test it with the target users. In this phase, the researchers provided access to second-year English program students enrolled in the IES course, ensured students and lecturer have registered accounts for accessing the platform, guiding students through the use of different pages: login, welcome, about, I watch, I listen, I read, and I speak. In addition, by this phase the researchers observed student interactions with the platform, and gathered feedback on usability and functionality of the website.

Last, the evaluation phase aimed to evaluate the feasibility and effectiveness of the web-based learning platform. In the evaluation, researchers engaged six experts and 64 university students to assess the platform based on three indicators: web design, instructional content, and English language use in the instructional design. Those lecturers were two experts in multimedia and informatics; while the four others were two experts in instructional content of English teaching and two lecturers in English linguistic expertise. Meanwhile, those students becoming respondents were the second graders of the English Language Education Study Program at a state university in Indonesia who were taking the IES course. They were also asked to rate the website developed in terms of its design, content, and language. Five measurement scales ranged from 1 to 5 respectively representing strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, strongly agree were used to rate 15 questions regarding with those three indicators. It means the higher score given the better evaluation result. Then, ratings from experts and students were examined by using paired sample t-test to find out its difference whether their ratings were consistent or not.

Figure 1. Five phases of ADDIE model

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This part reveals the result of the study, and the discussion confirming the result on the related previous studies. This part also shows exactly how to develop a prototype product using the ADDIE model, specifically a website for practicing intermediate-level English speaking. The result analysis also details how the website was developed through the five phases of research and development: analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation, as elaborated respectively.

3.1. Analysis

In this phase, the researchers focused on analyzing the students' need to learn English, especially in the practice of speaking skill, in terms of learning material, content, and learning platform. Ten questions were asked of students to be answered, which is depicted in Figure 2. The provided analysis revealed insights into student perceptions regarding the learning materials and platforms in the IES course. Most students (88%) found the learning materials difficult to understand. Consequently, there was unanimous agreement (100%) on the necessity of designing and including these materials on a website platform for better English practice. In terms of the learning platform, the data showed that 100% of students reported their lecturers had never used ICT for teaching and speaking practice. Nonetheless, a minority (28%) had experienced web-based learning for speaking practice in the IES class. Notably, only 22% of students had previously practiced speaking using a website platform, reflecting limited exposure to such tools. Despite these gaps, all students (100%) agreed on the need for a website platform to facilitate their speaking practice in the IES course. This alignment confirmed a strong demand for web-based learning mediums. The analysis depicted in Figure 1 underscored the necessity for a comprehensive website platform that integrated instructional content tailored to the students' needs. Thus, a web-based speaking practice tool for the Intermediate English-Speaking course was developed to address these needs effectively.

The analysis phase revealed a significant demand for a dedicated speaking practice platform, with data showing that a substantial majority of students found existing learning materials difficult and had minimal exposure to web-based speaking tools. This insight underscores the necessity for a specialized platform as

developed by this study which directly addresses these challenges. These platforms provide structured, contextually relevant materials and functionalities [1], [22].

Figure 2. Result of need analysis

3.2. Design

In this phase, the researchers designed the website layout and flow using wireframes as illustrated in the Figure 3 where the flowchart outlines the interactions and procedures among three entities: "lecturer", "system", and "student" within a structured system. As depicted by Figure 3, for the lecturer, the process initiates with a login action. Upon entering login details, authentication is performed by the system. If the credentials are correct, the lecturer is directed to the welcome page; otherwise, the process returns to the login page. Following successful authentication, the lecturer can manage IES course contents, including adding, editing, viewing, and deleting them. This course management operation is looped to facilitate continuous activity.

The system section administrates the login details for both lecturers and students, confirming their credentials and subsequently directing them to the welcome page. The primary functionalities available within the system include course management for lecturers-encompassing adding, editing, viewing, and deleting pages-and page viewing options for students. Moreover, individual pages such as the login page, I-listen page, I-watch page, I-read page, and I-speak page cater to specific actions within the system.

For the student, the procedure also commences with a login action, followed by authentication. Successful login leads the student to the welcome page, while incorrect login information redirects them back to the login page. Within the system, students can explore available course materials and access detailed information regarding each course material. The section concludes with a logout action where both lecturers and students can log out completing the process and leading to the end of the system. In summary, this flowchart clearly shows the detailed steps lecturers and students go through, from logging in and handling IES course materials, all the way to logging out, offering a straightforward view of how the system works.

The system flow in the design was meticulously developed to ensure a seamless user experience. The platform's layout and interactions were designed to mimic a classroom environment, including distinct sections for listening, watching, reading, and speaking. These elements are crucial for sustaining learner engagement and providing a comprehensive multimodal learning experience, which Mayer [4] suggests is essential for effective learning. By leveraging multimedia content, the website designed by this study supports the cognitive integration of auditory and visual information, enhancing comprehension and retention [7], [23].

3.3. Development

The prototype product developed from this study is a web-based English learning medium aimed at enhancing English speaking skills. The website, titled "Harati Speaking," can be accessed at <https://haratispeaking.com>. The primary objective of developing this website is to facilitate students practice

in English speaking by offering content tailored to their mastery level, which in this case is intermediate. The development of the learning material is guided by the course syllabus and is structured around two models of speaking practice: integrated speaking and independent speaking. Upon completing the web design, researchers and developer uploaded the learning materials via the lecturer dashboard after logging into the front page. Lecturers contributed to the content by attaching videos, audio, and instructional materials designed to help students practice their speaking skills. Table 1 provides an overview of the content development for various subject matters incorporated into the web platform, following the speaking practice models offered to students.

The learning materials, as depicted in Table 1, are integrated into each pre-designed page by aligning the content with the respective pages. Once the learning materials are fully developed and incorporated into the platform, the website is ready for testing. This involves implementing the website with the students enrolled in the IES class.

The development phase saw the incorporation of the design elements into a functional platform, supported by a robust backend that allows for continuous content updates. This phase also involved the collaboration with lecturers to develop relevant instructional content, further ensuring that the material aligns with the learners' academic curriculum and proficiency level. The platform offers two models of speaking practice: integrated speaking, which combines speaking with listening skills; and independent speaking, which encourages learners to develop their speaking skills using prompts and their own perceptions [13], [14].

Figure 3. The system flow of the website

Table 1. The development of learning materials tested in the platform

No.	Models of speaking practice in the web platform	Content of learning contexts	Learning objectives
1.	<p>Integrated speaking model:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Integrated speaking is the model of speaking practice integrated with listening skill. – Students watch the instructional videos in “I watch” with the related topics assigned to practice. – Students should listen to an audio podcast in “I listen.” – Students may start practicing speaking, as exemplified by the prompting video in “I watch.” – Students are recommended to read the guideline in “I read” what to tell regarding the topic assigned. – Students deliver their spontaneous speech in the “I speak” based on the guideline of what to speak. 	<p>Telling opinion: News</p> <p>Telling experience: Course requirement</p> <p>Telling preference: Cities</p>	<p>Students are able to express their opinions by telling or stating agreement and disagreement about ‘news’ as the topic.</p> <p>Students are able to express their experience in integrated speaking by telling or stating specific reasons and examples about ‘course requirement’ as the topic.</p> <p>Students are able to express their preference in integrated speaking by stating specific reasons and details about ‘cities’ as the topic.</p>
2.	<p>Independent speaking model:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Independent speaking is the model of speaking practice where students develop their speaking skill independently based on data, facts, and their own perceptions. – Students watch prompting videos on related topics provided by a lecturer in the “I watch.” – Students are recommended to read the data or facts in “I read,” where these data or facts are used to prompt their idea to speak but are not limited to such data or facts. – Students deliver their spontaneous speech in the “I speak” independently but limited to the assigned topic. 	<p>Telling opinion: Covid-19 vaccination</p> <p>Telling preference: Traveling</p> <p>Telling report: Climate change</p>	<p>Students are able to state their opinions independently by describing a situation or opinion about the ‘COVID-19 vaccination’ in addition to giving examples related to the topic.</p> <p>Students are able to express their preference in independent speaking by choosing between two options or more about ‘traveling’ as the topic and by explaining the reasons for the preference.</p> <p>Students are able to report a situation or a phenomenon in independent speaking by summarizing news or footage video about ‘climate change’ as the topic and report it based on their own perception.</p>

3.4. Implementation

The implementation phase involves putting the developed materials into action among the target students, who are second-year students in the English program taking the IES course. This phase is important as it ensures the materials on the website can be effectively utilized if they are well-constructed and suitable for the intended users [24]. Below is the description of seven pages implemented for users, screenshots of each page, and the sub-pages that have been tested while the speaking class is running.

3.4.1. Login page

The login page serves as the front page of the website. When users navigate to <https://haratispeaking.com>, they are directed to this page as shown on Figure 4. All students, who are respondents in this web development, have been pre-registered on the platform to access it via the login page. They must use their last name as the username and their student register number as the password. Students who are not registered by the web developers cannot access the platform. Similarly, lecturers need to register using their last name and lecturer base number to use the platform as instructors.

Figure 4. Login page of the website

3.4.2. Welcome page

After logging in, students are greeted by the welcome page, which provides an overview of the website and its content, designed to help students practice speaking English. This page, as shown on Figure 5, outlines the lessons structured around current issues and relevant topics. The left sidebar features several menus such as about, I listen, I watch, I read, and I speak. These menus serve as navigation options for the web-based learning journey. Upon completing activities in each menu, users are directed to the next menu as per the instructions on the completed page.

Figure 5. Welcome page of the website

3.4.3. About page

The "about" page, as shown on Figure 6, provides information about two models of speaking practice: integrated speaking and independent speaking. Integrated speaking combines speaking with listening skills, while independent speaking is enhanced without audio prompts, relying on data from charts, diagrams, or tables. Integrated speaking must be completed first.

Figure 6. The 'about' page

3.4.4. I watch page

The "I watch" page, as shown on Figure 7, includes videos designed to guide and facilitate student learning. Each video, lasting between 5 to 7 minutes, features instructional content from a lecturer. In integrated speaking, only instructional videos are provided, while the independent speaking model includes a prompting video related to each topic, illustrating how to manage speech on similar topics.

3.4.5. I listen page

The "I listen" page provides a list of audios that may include conversations, brief lectures, or reportages. This page, as shown on Figure 8, supports the integrated speaking model, using audios to prompt students' speaking practice. Each audio clip lasts for two to four minutes. At the end of each audio, a lecturer poses a prompting question, encouraging students to think about how they would respond.

3.4.6. I read page

The "I read" page offers learning materials like documents, pictures, charts, and diagrams in PDF format. These materials help students practice independent speaking, allowing them to manage their ideas based on personal opinions. The page, as shown on Figure 9, also contains documents sourced from relevant and current issues such as COVID-19 vaccination and climate change.

Figure 7. The "I watch" page

Figure 8. The "I listen" page

Figure 9. The "I read" page

3.4.7. I speak page

This page, as depicted in Figure 10, is the core of the website. Here, students can deliver, record, and save their spoken responses on the platform. Students can start recording their voices upon entering this page (Figure 10(a)) and are required to fill in their names and the topic of their speech (Figure 10(b)). The recorded audio is then saved to the platform by clicking the "insert audio" button (Figure 10(b)). The platform automatically saves all student voice recordings, which lecturers can monitor through their dashboard (Figure 10(c)). Lecturers can also replay these recordings for class evaluations and progress analysis.

By implementing the "Harati Speaking" website with a targeted group of second-year students, the study provides real-world insights into the usability and effectiveness of the learning tools. This practical application mirrors similar methodologies observed in the design and deployment of blended learning environments using the ADDIE-RP model in Bangladesh's TVET sector [18]. Such implementations reveal the pragmatic aspects of the design, allowing iterative enhancements based on user feedback, a critical component in educational technology deployment.

Figure 10. Overview of the 'I speak' feature where students can deliver, record, and save their speech: (a) "I speak" page; (b) "I speak" sub-page; and (c) "I speak" page on the lecturer dashboard

3.5. Evaluation

The final phase of this research involves evaluating the feasibility of the product through assessments by experts and ratings from student users. Six experts (referred to as N1's mean of ratings) evaluated the product based on their specialized knowledge, while 64 students (referred to as N2's mean of ratings) used the website in their IES class. The evaluation focused on three key indicators: web design, instructional content, and the English language used on the website.

The results show, as depicted in Table 2, that both experts and students find the web design effective, with experts giving a slightly higher mean score. The highest score of 5.00 by experts in terms of cognitive development and ease of use suggests that the design is well-tailored for EFL learners. The minor difference between expert and student scores ($p > 0.05$) implies similar perceptions regarding the website's design feasibility. Therefore, the web prototype is regarded eligible from a design perspective, supporting ease of use and cognitive appropriateness for EFL learners.

As shown in Table 3, the evaluations reveal a high level of satisfaction with the instructional content of the website from both experts and students, with students rating it slightly higher on average. The alignment of materials with intermediate-level English-speaking practice and adherence to the course syllabus highlight the effectiveness of the instructional content. The clear audio and informative videos contribute to a practical learning experience. The high means and insignificant p-values ($p > 0.05$) confirm that both groups consider the same evaluation perception to the instructional content which is highly feasible.

Table 4 depicts that the evaluation of language use by both experts and students shows high feasibility, with mean scores slightly above 4.60. The structure of English sentences and vocabulary used on the website are regarded appropriate for intermediate-level EFL learners. Importantly, the language is free from bias and promotes effective and simple communication. The insignificant difference between expert and student evaluations ($p > 0.05$) suggests a compromise on the suitability of the language. Thus, the website's use of language is confirmed to be effective and appropriate for its intended purpose since the language use underscores its clarity, appropriateness, and non-discriminatory nature. Overall, the evaluation of the "Harati Speaking", a prototype website for English language learning, demonstrates high feasibility across web design, instructional content, and language use. The consistent ratings from both experts and students indicate that the website is a practical and effective tool for facilitating English-speaking practice among university-level EFL learners. The slight differences in mean scores of three indicator assessed by experts and students are statistically insignificant, confirming a shared positive perception of the website's functionalities and content. These results ensure that the platform's design and content are not only pedagogically sound but also user-friendly and engaging since it involved structured feedbacks from both experts and students as users [25]–[28].

Table 2. The evaluation of web design

No.	Indicators evaluated	Mean N1	Mean N2	p-value
1.	The website's front page attracts users' attention as English learners.	4.67	4.53	.360
2.	Website design can stimulate users' understanding as English learners.	4.33	4.71	
3.	The website corresponds to the level of cognitive development of users as English learners.	5.00	4.38	
4.	The website is easy to use by users as English learners.	5.00	4.00	
5.	The website is very practical to support users to practice English speaking.	4.33	4.43	
Mean average		4.67	4.41	

Table 3. The evaluation of instructional content

No.	Indicators evaluated	Mean N1	Mean N2	p-value
1.	Website content delivery material aligns with the user level for English-speaking practice at the intermediate level.	5.00	4.53	.599
2.	The material presented through audio is clearly audible to listen to and follows the user's level of English-speaking practice.	4.33	4.84	
3.	Videos on the website can illustrate the content and objectives of learning English speaking skill.	4.33	4.38	
4.	The content of the audio and video materials provided on the website has followed the syllabus for learning English speaking skill at the intermediate level.	4.33	5.00	
5.	The learning instructions given on each menu on the website are clear and can be understood by users to practice English speaking skill.	5.00	4.84	
Mean average		4.60	4.72	

Table 4. Evaluation related to the language use

No.	Indicators evaluated	Mean N1	Mean N2	p-value
1.	The structure of English sentences used on the website is easy for users to understand for English speaking practice at the intermediate level.	5.00	4.71	.774
2.	The English language presented on the website does not contain racism and intolerance to users and does not harass gender.	4.33	4.84	
3.	The English language used by the website is in accordance with the level of thinking and social-emotional development of users.	4.33	4.43	
4.	The English language is narrated using effective and simple sentences.	4.33	4.38	
5.	The vocabulary used is practical vocabulary that is commonly used on educational websites.	5.00	4.84	
Mean average		4.60	4.64	

Referring to all phases of the ADDIE model reported by this study, it exemplifies how technological innovation can be harnessed to enhance language education. The structured five-phase approach of the ADDIE model ensures thorough consideration of learner needs and systematic content delivery. This meticulous framework underpins the platform's development, making it a notable contribution to the field of educational technology.

To compare with other generalized language platforms such as Duolingo and Rosetta Stone, "Harati Speaking" website is distinct in its targeted approach toward intermediate-level learners, offering tailored content that aligns with their proficiency. Duolingo and Rosetta Stone [11] excel in providing broad-spectrum language learning through gamified and immersive content. They often lack the depth and specificity of targeting particular learner levels and integrating instructional design methodologies, as effectively demonstrated by "Harati Speaking". In contrast to Duolingo, which incorporates gamification to enhance user engagement, "Harati Speaking" integrates pedagogically sound methods to address specific speaking requirements of intermediate learners. This focus on specialization is similar to [19] that adapts the ADDIE

model in developing a platform for Arabic language learning for tourism. Their research underscored the importance of addressing specific language learning needs, similar to how "Harati Speaking" caters to intermediate English learners by providing contextually relevant materials and functionalities.

Similarly, the study in the context of TVET in Bangladesh [18], which integrates rapid prototyping with ADDIE for a blended learning environment, underscores the flexibility and effectiveness of the ADDIE model. By paralleling the structured yet adaptive nature of this approach, "Harati Speaking" not only ensures comprehensive content delivery but also builds in mechanisms for continuous improvement and responsiveness to user feedback. By implementing the "Harati Speaking" website with a targeted group of second-year students, the study provides real-world insights into the usability and effectiveness of the learning tools. This practical application mirrors similar methodologies observed in the design and deployment of blended learning environments using the ADDIE-RP model in Bangladesh's TVET sector [18]. Such implementations reveal the pragmatic aspects of the design, allowing iterative enhancements based on user feedback, a critical component in educational technology deployment.

Referring to the result evaluation, the "Harati Speaking" platform demonstrates remarkable relevance and applicability in modern educational contexts, where the integration of ICT in language learning can bridge significant gaps, especially in speaking skills. Platforms developed with the ADDIE model have been shown to offer structured and effective learning experiences due to their systematic approach to addressing instructional challenges [29]. In addition, given the structured development anchored in a robust educational philosophy, "Harati Speaking" presents itself as more than just a digital tool; it is a pedagogically sound learning environment encouraging active student engagement. This aligns with the cognitive theory of multimedia learning [9], which emphasizes the integration of dual channels (visual and auditory) for effective learning. Upcoming research could engage in comparative studies between "Harati Speaking" and other established language learning tools to identify unique value propositions. For instance, a comparative study might explore how the structured ADDIE-based development of "Harati Speaking" results in better learning outcomes or user engagement compared to the more gamified, and less structured approaches of platforms. Longitudinal studies examining the long-term impact of the platform on language proficiency could provide deeper insights into its effectiveness and sustainability. Such studies could adopt frameworks used in blended learning environments within TVET sectors, as documented in [18], to understand the platform's ability to maintain learner engagement and motivation over prolonged periods.

4. CONCLUSION

This research has successfully developed a prototype of a web-based language learning product named "Harati Speaking" to support students practicing English speaking in the intermediate level class. To ensure that the website prototype has fulfilled a good development of the product, the development and deployment of the "Harati Speaking" platform via the ADDIE model exemplify a dedicated and systematic approach to addressing specific educational needs. It highlights the model's strength in creating structured, effective, and user-friendly educational tools. The platform's positive reception, backed by rigorous evaluations, underscores its feasibility in facilitating English-speaking practice among intermediate learners. However, several shortcomings in this study could potentially impact results. Firstly, the sample size was limited to 64 students, which may not be representative of the broader population. This limitation could lead to skewed results that cannot be generalized. Additionally, the reliance on self-reported data for the initial need's analysis phase introduces potential biases. If students over- or under-reported their needs or experiences, it could have influenced the development of the website. Furthermore, the study did not account for varying levels of technological proficiency among students, which might affect their ability to effectively use the platform and thus their overall performance. Regardless of its shortcomings, the successful implementation and positive reception of the 'Harati Speaking' website confirm its potential as a valuable resource for EFL educators and learners, meeting the unmet need for dedicated speaking practice tools and promoting better learning outcomes. Future research could further explore long-term impacts and comparative effectiveness with broader populations to continue refining and enhancing this innovative educational tool.

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